

DESIGN AND ANALYSIS OF A SCALED SMART ROTOR BLADE FOR WIND TURBINE LOAD CONTROL

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SUMMARY

Experiments on a scaled wind turbine are conducted to research the Smart Rotor Concept. The design requirements for the rotor are severe because the blade will be highly loaded, must also be scaled dynamically and actuators and sensors must be fit. Analyses of the design show that both the strength and dynamic requirements can be met and the blades are manufactured.

Keywords: Wind Turbines, Smart Rotor Blades, Aerodynamic Loads, FE Analysis

INTRODUCTION

Currently, horizontal axis wind turbine (HAWT) manufacturers are facing several challenges related to both a fast increase in turbine size (see Figure 1) and market growth. The trends force manufacturers to upscale existing blade designs. However, the boundaries of current technologies are being approached.

For large turbines the biggest design drive is already fatigue. This is because on top of the mean aerodynamic load there are several disturbances that cause dynamic deflections of the blade and thus fluctuations in the stress distribution. Current blades are dimensioned for at least 10^8 cycles. These disturbances are caused by changes in the wind field and by the rotation of the blade through this wind field. Examples of these are wind shear, yaw misalignment, tower shadow and fluctuations in inflow. Additionally, mass effects will play an ever larger role in the design of turbines. For instance, historically the mass of blades has increased with the rotor diameter to the power 2.4 [1] to 2.65 [2], depending on how the trend line is fitted. Since the blade rotates with respect to the gravitational field, this also adds to fatigue. The fatigue loads induced by the aerodynamics will also increase with increasing size, for instance through the more severe wind shear experienced by large machines.

Figure 1: The increase of turbine state of the art size in time. Figure adapted from van Kuik in [3]

Mitigating the amplitude of the fluctuations could therefore lead to a longer service life of blades, but also to lighter blades. On wind turbines already some features are applied to control the loads. Passive systems like stall control have been in use for a while. Today, most large turbines are installed with the possibility to control their rotational speed to operate at optimal tip speed ratios at wind speeds below the rated wind speed and pitch control to alleviate loads above rated wind speeds. However, pitch control requires heavy hydraulics and bearings and only actuation speeds up to 1P (once per rotation) are possible.

Therefore the following new concept is proposed: by controlling the aerodynamics at different stations along the blade's span the way the blade is loaded can be controlled, counter-acting the disturbances and mitigating fatigue loads. This, in combination with appropriate sensors that measure the loads or deformations and a controller that computes an actuation signal, is defined as the 'smart' rotor concept. Such an aerodynamic load control (ALC) system has been intensively researched for helicopter blades and recently also feasibility studies for wind turbine blades have been made [4], [5], [6], [7]. The goals of the system would be to react both to deterministic loads, such as wind shear and tower shadow, as to indeterministic loads such as gusts.

To investigate the feasibility of the concept experiments on scaled turbine blades are performed. In previous experiments [8] [9], performed on a non-rotating blade, the potential of the concept was proven, but this experiment did not include the rotor dynamics and the interaction between the wake and the rotor plane. In this paper we will focus on the design of experiments, to be conducted on a scaled turbine which will be employed to investigate these effects.

EXPERIMENT SET-UP

In order to investigate the load reduction potential of the smart rotor concept it was decided to build a scaled turbine which will be tested in the TU Delft's Open Jet Facility. Scaling does not only apply to the size and operational settings, but also to the dynamics of the blade.

The frequencies of the disturbances to which a turbine blade is subjected, such as wind shear, tower shadow and yaw misalignment, are often related to the rotational frequencies of the turbine. Moreover, the proximity of the blade's natural first mode(s) to these frequencies make scaling of the blade's dynamic behavior needed in order to study the smart rotor concept in a correct manner on a scaled size. The rotational frequency on rated speed and first flapping frequency of the full scale reference turbine are 0.20 and 0.69Hz respectively. The rotational speed of the scaled rotor is set at 7Hz, which sets the target for the first bending mode to 24Hz. Reynolds scaling was not employed, nor scaling to the reduced frequencies. But the reduced frequencies are higher for the scaled blade. This means that the lag in the aerodynamic to the blade's motion is also larger.

The deformation of the continuously deformable flaps was achieved by inducing strain in a piezo electric patch in a so called Thunder actuator. This is a laminated piezo electric bender actuator and it forms the suction side surface of the deformable part of the blade's surface. Two distinct flaps will be implemented. Thus, suppression of higher harmonics (e.g. second bending mode) is also possible, but we will focus on the first flapwise bending mode.

DESIGN AND MANUFACTURING OF AN AERO-ELASTICLY TAILORED BLADE

Because of experiences obtained with previous experiments [9] a similar design and production concept was implemented.

Conceptual Structural Design

The blade's structure consisted of a glass weave, wrapped around a foam core, infused in a doubly rigid mould using Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Moulding (VARTM). The foam core was fitted with a steel foot which was used to mount the blade to the hub. Holes were drilled through the foam to fit the sensor and actuator cables as well as a safety cable. The outboard section of the blade was kept straight and equipped with a glass-epoxy spar. The spar was prefabricated and assembled with the foam core and steel inserts before infusion of the skin. The spar has three functions. Firstly, the aft part of the blade is cut out in the outboard section to fit the actuators. The spar serves as mounting point for these actuators. Secondly, it reinforces the blades circumference where the slots are cut out. And finally it acts as added mass. This is required to lower the frequency of the first flapping mode of the blade, which we are interested in.

Materials

The employed fiber material is an E-glass 8H satin weave, specifically the SS303 by Ten Cate Advanced Composites. The used resin is the Bakelite ERP/EPH 04908. The resin has a long pot life, which is needed in the infusion process. The foam which forms the blade's core is Airex C70.200 PVC foam with a density of 200kg/m³. This is a relatively dense foam, which is required in order to attain high tolerances during milling and to prevent wrinkling of the skin.

Aerodynamic design

One of the analyses performed in the design of the blade was determining the outer shape of the blade. The twist and chord distribution were primarily based on the aerodynamic performance of the turbine and derived using a BEM based optimizer. The absolute thickness of the blade was left open to be determined in the structural optimization process. However, it turned out that to obtain the desired structural properties a slender DU96-W180 profile along the whole span of the aerofoil was required. Another restriction was the fact that to successfully implement the actuators in the tip, a straight tip - without twist and taper - was desired. Due to the restrictions mentioned above, attaining an aerodynamically optimal design turned out to be impossible. But obtaining an optimally performing turbine was not the goal of this research project, so the design was adapted to fit the shape requirements.

Actuator design

Camber control was achieved by sawing slots at two locations in the blade's straight outboard section and filling these with actuators based on piezo electric materials. These so called Thunder actuators were placed in line with the suction side of the aerodynamic profile. See Figure 2.

Figure 2: Design of the new actuator. a) Cross section. b) Fabricated test-section

The curvature of the actuators fairly coincides with the curvature of the profile. Placing the actuators here would assure a smooth and solid surface. This is needed for predictable performance of the actuator and to have a qualitatively good boundary layer over the actuator. In previous experiments the Thunder was placed in the center and the shape of both the pressure and suction side was matched with foam that was covered with an elastomeric skin. This gave unsatisfactory results. In this case, the slight mismatch in surface curvature between the baseline profile and actuator surface was allowed for in order to obtain a hard, smooth surface.

The remainder of the aft profile shape is achieved by filling the slot with foam and covering it with a PP film. Two types of foam were implemented: dissected rigid PVC

foam filled the largest part of the space, which was covered with a soft polystyrene foam patch to smoothen the sections of the rigid foam. See Figure 2.

The actuator was firstly applied in a polymeric test section. This allowed for the identification of the actuator system, as well as designing a controller for the system.

Redesign for safety

The previous blade used in the on-rotating experiments failed. The failure mechanism was found to be an adhesive fracture between the laminate and the aluminium foot insert, in combination with splitting of the laminate at the trailing edge. The split could occur by matrix cracking because all splices were placed on the trailing edge. See Figure 3.

Figure 3: Failure mode of the previous blade

However, the blade used in the experiments here, would be mounted on a rotating hub, subjecting it to severe centrifugal loading and posing serious safety issues should it structurally fail. Therefore several measures were taken to assure structural soundness and safety:

- The blade foot geometry and the laminate around it, was chosen such that shape locking of the foot inside the laminate was assured. Additionally, a roving was wrapped around the laminate at this position to additionally reinforce the laminate in circumferential direction.
- Lap shear specimens on the strength of the metal/glass-epoxy interface are produced and tested with each blade.
- The location of splices was chosen such that there were no coincidental splices on the inboard part of the blade. See Figure 4. This is very important because the skin only consists of two plies and strength is a critical issue.

The cross splices on the pressure side are needed because otherwise the main part cannot be cut out in one piece.

- As a final safety precaution, a cable will run from the foot to the tip insert.

Figure 4: Splice location on suction and pressure side

DETERMINATION OF THE LAMINATE LAY-UP

The Finite Element model

A model of the blade was constructed in Ansys [10], using quadratic shell elements for the skin laminate and quadratic brick elements to model the foam core. To determine the contour of the core, the outer contour of the blade is reduced with the laminate thickness. The surface of covering shell elements are set to coincide with the bottom side of the laminate which they represent. Thus, the top layer of the elements coincides with outer contour of the blade.

The load case was obtained from the same BEM analysis that was used to determine the aerodynamic design. The load case consists of static loading, whereas the model will be subjected to fluctuating loads. A certain safety margin should therefore be kept.

For the determination of the natural modes, a modal analysis is run, including prestressing effects from the static analysis. Both the static and dynamic analyses are used to optimize the number of plies that form the skin of the blade.

Model's results

The outcome of the optimization process was that the skin should consist of two plies. The ply thickness of the satin weave processed in this manner is 0.25mm, so the laminate thickness is 0.5mm.

The results of the static analysis are compared to the respective maximum stresses of the employed glass/epoxy laminate. As can be seen in Table 1, the respective stresses stay well within the strength limits of the material. However, it should be noted that this is the results for a static load case under nominal load conditions. No predictions of the fatigue life are made.

Wrinkling is another critical failure mode for thin walled structures with a foam core. According to Fagerberg [11] compressive failure, rather than skin wrinkling will typically occur with dense foam types, like the ones implemented here. But the skin is very thin in this case, increasing the possibility of wrinkling. The critical compressive wrinkling stress according to formula derived by Plantema is 677MPa, higher than the compressive strength.

Table 1: Maximum occurring stresses and material's strength

	Max. occurring stress	Material strength
Tension	31MPa	392MPa
Compression	24MPa	476MPa
Shear	14MPa	94MPa

The eigenmodes are evaluated by performing a modal analysis. The results of this analysis can be seen in Table 2 and Figure 5. The prediction of first natural frequency is slightly higher than the target frequency of 24Hz. However, linear modal analyses overestimate the eigenfrequencies. Moreover, the eigenfrequency of the blade can be tuned easily by adding mass locally. This also lowers the eigenfrequencies.

Table 2: Description of the first three natural modes.

	Natural frequency	Mode description
First mode	33Hz	First flapwise bending mode (Figure 5)
Second mode	92Hz	First edgewise bending mode
Third mode	157Hz	Second flapwise bending mode

Figure 5: First vibration mode of the blade

MANUFACTURING

The infusion was performed using VARTM. The RTM unit was set to infuse with constant speed but with a certain threshold value on the pressure. When the injection pressure reaches this threshold, the RTM unit controls the flow such that the pressure remains at this constant injection pressure. Both values – initial volume flow and pressure threshold value - are chosen such that the injection takes place at low rate, but that the pot life of the resin is not exceeded.

The critical issue with comparison to usual VARTM is that the thickness of the laminate is very small, only 0.5mm and that one of the solid surfaces between which the laminate is infused consists of foam. The foam is relatively flexible and preassembled before the dry preform is wrapped around it.

These critical issues resulted in the occurrence of dry spots. Vacuum infusion in a test set-up on a foam substrate was performed with excess fixation spray applied and a piece of metal clamped on top of the vacuum bag. The combination of pressure and fixation spray proved to be too big of an obstruction for the resin flow locally and led to inclusion of dry spots. To prevent this, we decided to pay additional care when assembling the core elements, to sand the foam locally and to use a minimum of fixation spray.

Assembly of the core elements is very important because the laminate thickness is only 0.5mm. Any misalignment in the core will therefore lead to locally high pressures when the mould is closed and the core with the 0.5mm thick dry preform around it has to be forced in the mould cavity's shape.

Results

The first blade for testing was successfully produced. See Figure 6.

Figure 6: Finished blade (without actuators)

The skin laminate's fabric was void free, but some badly filled areas were observed in the UD that was wrapped around the foot. However, for the reinforcing function of these filaments this is not a critical issue.

CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

A blade was designed and analyzed. The analysis predicts that the blade will meet the strength and dynamic requirements. Manufacturing of the blade was quite critical, but good specimens have been produced.

The blade will be tested both in static deflection and dynamically. Dynamic testing will focus both on the dynamic behaviour – including sensor performance - and on the fatigue life of the blade. A comparison with the results of the FEA will be made.

Two specimens will subsequently be equipped with sensors and actuators and employed in aero-elastic experiments.

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